

LINGUISTIC INTEGRATION IN TECHNICAL EDUCATION: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of teaching specialized subjects in English through ensuring interdisciplinary integration and close interconnection between academic disciplines. The author analyzes methodological approaches aimed at strengthening the integration of subject knowledge and language learning in modern education, adapting the content of education to the requirements of professional activity, and developing students' professional communicative competence. Furthermore, the didactic possibilities of effectively organizing interdisciplinary integration in the process of teaching specialized subjects in English are identified, and practical recommendations and proposals aimed at implementing this process are developed.

Keywords: terminology, specialist, professional texts, labor market, worldview, higher education, project, professional training, reading, writing, comprehension, grammar, lexicology, problems, solutions, modern period, communication, environment, modern specialists, pedagogical mastery, critical analysis, discussion, interest, question-answer method, text, vocabulary, organization.

Introduction.

As the world evolves, the boundaries of knowledge are also changing. People's priorities and worldviews regarding education are also expanding. The demand for knowledge of foreign languages is particularly growing. Today, higher educational institutions face the task of training highly qualified specialists. In professional activities, knowing foreign languages helps to stay informed about the latest discoveries. This will allow for their discussion with specialists from various

countries and the study of global experience. The professional training of competitive and in-demand personnel in the modern labor market through the study of foreign languages remains a vital and important factor; therefore, considering modern methods of teaching foreign languages and developing the most appropriate methodology for teaching specialized disciplines in foreign languages based on them is becoming one of the most pressing issues in today's education.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review).

In the scientific research of foreign scholars J. Culler, S. Kangisser, G. Leech, and H.P. Grice, the problems of pragmalinguistics are revealed, specifically the socio-cultural, psychological, and linguistic aspects of defining the meanings of words in a text and forming communicative competence. In the scientific research of scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States, such as E.S. Aznaurova, L.M. Vasilev, A.I. Vlasenkov, T.B. Dudina, I.A. Zimnyaya, L.G. Luzina, V.N. Marov, V. Myasnikov, O.I. Okulovsky, M.A. Pautova, and G.G. Pocheptsov, the socio-pedagogical and integral-pedagogical aspects of forming students' competence have been deeply researched. These scholars have developed a student-centered approach to the educational process, a competency-based educational model, and theoretical and methodological foundations aimed at improving professional training. Furthermore, foreign scholars such as V. Chandra Sekhar Rao, Jame W. Porcaro, as well as domestic researchers G. Dadamirzaev, K. Fayzullaev and A. Hasanov studied the issues of teaching specialized subjects in English, that is, the organization of professionally oriented language education. Their scientific works highlight the integration of English with professional activity, the teaching of specialized terminology, the implementation of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) methodology into the educational process, and the theoretical and practical foundations for developing students' professional communicative competencies. These studies are of great importance in the scientific substantiation of the pedagogical and methodological aspects of teaching specialized subjects in a foreign language. At the same time, issues of further improving the integration of specialized

subjects and a foreign language in the modern higher education system, applying innovative pedagogical technologies, and preparing students for the international professional environment remain relevant. Therefore, this article analyzes the methodological foundations of teaching specialized subjects in English, existing problems, and effective pedagogical solutions aimed at their elimination.

Research Methodology.

The problem of low results in mastering specialized subjects in foreign languages at technical universities in our country can have two solutions: organizational and methodological. On the organizational side, existing results can be improved by redistributing the time allocated for practical sessions, and on the other hand, by eliminating bias in the methodology used in organizing independent and practical work. From a methodological standpoint, it is necessary to improve textbooks, teaching aids, and instructions intended for mastering the subject, and to create textbooks consisting of simple, fluent, and interesting tasks that are understandable to the student. Various gadgets in the development of information and communication technologies In the development of information and communication technologies, it is necessary to effectively use various gadgets, smartphones, and other equipment. Therefore, in order to increase the interest of young people in education, it is necessary to create electronic textbooks and thermal dictionaries and enrich the material and methodological content of each subject.

Another pressing issue is the development of motivation for students to learn foreign languages. Sometimes the territorial location of an educational institution can also play a key role in the emergence of a foreign-language communication environment. Therefore, even the artificial creation of such an environment, regardless of the geographical location of the university, allows for the formation of stable motivation for learning. From this perspective, one of the effective ways to create a foreign-language communication environment is to organize online and offline presentations, open lessons, international conferences, inter-university student exchanges, and interesting meetings in a foreign language.

Analysis and results.

Taking into account the specifics of teaching foreign languages in technical universities, according to J.A. Komensky, it is necessary to rely on the practice of granting independence in language learning, taking into account stages, utility, consistency, strength, and individual differences.¹ Also, in the theory put forward by Mackay: "The linguistic principle of taking into account the level of knowledge of the native language in the acquisition of foreign languages; the personal cognitive principle of the student; the emotional-psychological principle: the formation of the linguistic "I" (overcoming negative emotional factors such as fear of speaking in a foreign language and uncertainty) and the interconnected acquisition of the language and culture of the country of the language being studied."²

Based on the above principles, it is necessary to apply effective methods of teaching specialized subjects in foreign languages. This will guide the selection of appropriate teaching methods. A teaching method is a system of purposeful actions by a teacher that ensures the organization of educational activities for students, their mastery of educational content, and thereby the achievement of educational goals. Within the structure of each teaching method, it is possible to identify teaching methods that implement the content of the method in the lesson. Educational techniques are specific actions and operations of the teacher, the purpose of which is to convey knowledge, develop skills and abilities, and stimulate students' learning activities to solve specific problems of the educational process.

In modern didactic literature, there are many classifications of methods and techniques for teaching a foreign language (E.I. Passov, I.L. Bim, A.N. Shchukin, etc.). In particular, A.N. Shchukin divides teaching methods into 4 groups: direct (e.g., natural, audiovisual, audiolingual, etc.); conscious (grammatical-semantic, conscious-contrastive, etc.); estrodial (communicative, tandem method); and

¹ Comenius Ya.A. Selected Pedagogical Works. The "Anthology of Thinking" series. Moscow: "Urayt" Publishing House, 2019.

² Zakarneh B. Language ego as an obstacle to mastering English among students of Arab University. British English Linguistics Journal. 2018. Vol. 6. No. 3. PP. 40-55.

intensive (emotional-semantic, propositional-pedagogical, etc.).

Transcription.

At the transcription stage, the teacher introduces their students to the written or oral content. In many materials, the foreign text is located in the left half of the page, and the translation is on the right side.

Productive: Students speak and interact with themselves in the target language without interruptions or corrections. Simply put, it represents students' ability to communicate freely in foreign languages without fear of making mistakes. There are several ways to do this.

1. Audiolingual method based on the repetition of language structures;
2. The method of assimilation into the language environment;
3. The grammar-translation method, a natural method based on the systematic study of grammar, aimed at studying oral speech in the context of communication that is closest to reality;
4. Structural method based on the development of structural models.

It is advisable to use such methods in teaching specialized subjects in foreign languages. During the training, students are given a specific professional technical task, during which they will be able to reinforce their knowledge by reading, translating, and completing a series of relevant texts, as well as performing lexical exercises. Through this method, motivation for linguistic education is also formed through students' interest in their profession and chosen field.

One of the most pressing problems in teaching specialized subjects in foreign languages in non-philological universities is the shortage of specialists who are fluent in foreign languages. To eliminate this problem, the head of state and the higher education system are carrying out a number of measures.

In particular, any employee who has a certificate of language proficiency will receive a monthly salary bonus, and teachers who have created textbooks and manuals in foreign languages will be worthily rewarded. However, it is not easy for teachers to learn foreign languages in addition to their professional activities. The

solution to this is to create textbooks, manuals, thematic and terminological online and offline dictionaries, audio and video blogs based on artificial intelligence that can be used by both students and specialist teachers. Through such auxiliary manuals, any specialist can achieve a certain level of effectiveness in conducting professional education in foreign languages.

It is known from world experience. There is an ESP (Teaching English for Specific Purposes) methodology. As stated in the relevance of the issue, the reduction of English language hours should not be considered a problem. In the reduction of teaching hours, it is sufficient to explain the main terminology in the subject, teaching and learning issues in the given English language hours. The ESP methodology helps students develop skills such as speaking, writing, reading, understanding, and listening in English during the study of terms, concepts, etc., related to the field, by teaching specialized subjects taught in the 3rd and 4th years of study in English. The application of the ESP methodology in the field of technology serves as the basis for achieving the intended goal. Through this, the application of a clear mechanism for implementing interdisciplinary connectivity and integration.

Conclusions and suggestions. (Conclusion/Recommendations).

In conclusion, in order to keep pace with the times, it is possible to achieve the goal of training our students as mature personnel in accordance with world requirements by providing the most modern knowledge, organizing vocational education, and organizing the teaching of subjects related to the field in English. Since information about the most advanced machinery and technologies, new innovative developments is provided in English, it is necessary to integrate specialized subjects with English language subjects, to establish interdisciplinary relations. As noted above, reducing the number of English language hours serves as an alternative solution for developing the English language skills of trained personnel through the teaching of specialized subjects in English.

Literature.

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. Five important initiatives to improve the spirituality of youth and organize their leisure time meaningfully. Electronic resource: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2019/04/03/5-tashabbus/>

10 Kakhkharov A.A. Optimal method for increasing students' spatial imagination. International Scientific and Practical Conference. Tashkent 2013

11 Kakhkharov. A. A. Khidirov. C. Using SAPR AutoCAD in the practice of teaching graphic disciplines. 21st-century graphics. Abstracts of reports of the XIV All-Ukrainian Student Scientific and Technical Conference - Sevastopol.2011.145-147p.

12 Ortikov, N. B., & Amanzhanovna, I. D. (2022). MODERN TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF ENGLISH SCIENCE. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 1839-1846.

13 Amanzhanovna, I. D. (2022). Methodology for Using Modern Methods and Tools in Teaching English Language. Online Scientific Journal of Innovation in Social Sciences, 2 (6), 11-15.

14 Amanzhanovna, I. D. (2022). The Time for Developing and Monitoring Students' Knowledge in Teaching English Language